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LEVERAGING SATELLITE DATA FOR HYDRO-METEOROLOGICAL EXTREMES: INSIGHTS FROM DROUGHT AND FLOOD ANALYSIS IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the increased availability of free-of-charge satellite data has allowed the study of many natural and human-made processes at low cost and has boosted research in many fields. This study is mainly focussed on the ease of monitoring extreme weather events viz., Drought and Flood using satellite data. As we know, Drought represents the most pervasive hydro-meteorological phenomenon, marked by extended periods of water scarcity that severely affect natural resources, environment, and socio-economic stability. In this approach, satellite data products were leveraged to derive the PDSI (Palmer Drought Severity Index) and SPEI (Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index) for Coimbatore (11.0168° N, 76.9558° E), a tropical wet and dry climate region. Notably, the SPEI data were sourced from SPEIbase: Standardised Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index database, Version 2.9, while PDSI data were obtained from TerraClimate: Monthly Climate and Climatic Water Balance for Global Terrestrial Surfaces, University of Idaho. The data extraction and analysis were performed using a Machine Learning (ML) approach via Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform using Java scripting. Further, the monthly dynamics of SPEI and PDSI were computed over 1990 to 2021, using the modifiedmk package in R. The results indicated a significant increase trend in wetness over the study period. On the other hand, flood represents the most catastrophic natural disasters globally in terms of impact on human life and the economy. In light of mitigating the impacts, Global Flood Awareness System - GloFAS (Satellite-based real-time flood assessment tool) has been used in this study for computing the flooded areas and demarcation of flood affected taluks/villages in Kerala during Chooralmala landslide event (July 31 to August 1, 2024). GloFAS is the product of Copernicus Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) satellite data. The results infer that the total flooded areas for the particular area is about 106 sq.km and the land cover affected is about 105.6 sq.km. The output matched with 85% of the observational data as reported by the Kerala State Disaster Management Authority (KSDMA) through media. Therefore, these findings underscore the necessity of validating the obtained outputs for multiple locations, before the implementation of strategic planning measures to ensure the socio-economic resilience and highlight the importance of continuous monitoring and adaptation to evolving climatic conditions.

Keywords: Drought, Flood, GEE, GloFAS, PDSI, SPEI and SAR